

**RDA Minimal Metadata for Learning Resources Data Dictionary
October 2021**

	A	B	C	D	E
1	Name	Definition	Type	Usage notes, allowed values, examples, other constraints	<i>Suggested controlled vocabularies</i>
2	Title	The human readable name of the learning resource.	TEXT (1000)	<p>Notes: It should be transcribed from the learning resource itself or the descriptive metadata found on the resource landing page. If no title exists, the provider should create it. If the resource exists in more than one language, a separate record should be created for that version.</p> <p>Allowed values: Should be Unicode and allow for diacritics.</p> <p>Example: "CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide"</p> <p>Constraints: Not repeatable</p>	
3	Abstract / Description	A brief synopsis about or description of the learning resource.	TEXT (2000)	<p>Notes: The description can include the relationship of this resource to others, if applicable, e.g., a part within a series or collection, and the existence of translations of the resource into other languages.</p> <p>Allowed values: Should be Unicode and allow for diacritics.</p> <p>Example: "A guide designed by European experts to help social science researchers make their research data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR)."</p> <p>Constraints: Not repeatable</p>	
4	Author(s)	The name of entity(ies) authoring the learning resource.	TEXT	<p>Notes: Authors should be listed in the order presented on the resource or on the descriptive metadata on the landing page of the resource. Multiple authors should be listed with commas between the names. Names should include given or first name and family or surname, and a personal identifier such as an ORCID, if available. Some input systems may offer separate fields for each of these identifying items.</p> <p>Allowed values: Should be Unicode and allow for diacritics.</p> <p>Example: "CESSDA Training Team"</p> <p>Constraints: Repeatable</p>	<p>Evaluate: https://www.loc.gov/marc/relators/relaterm.html for author and more probably, for contributor for Extended Doc.</p>
5	Primary Language	The language in which the learning resource was originally published or made available.	TEXT (2)	<p>Notes: If the resource exists in more than one language, that information can be included in the Abstract/Description term. A second record should be created, if possible for the other language versions of the resource.</p> <p>Allowed values: String composed by a code as defined by the code set ISO 639-1:2002</p> <p>Example: "en"</p> <p>Constraints: Not repeatable</p>	

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6	Keyword(s)	The keyword(s) or tag(s) used to describe the learning resource.	TEXT (100)	<p>Notes: Keywords may be single words or phrases that characterize what the resource is about. Ideally, the keywords come from a controlled vocabulary of terms that are curated and structured to represent the specific nature of the collection of learning resources, e.g., by subject domain, data format and/or data type. In a web or searchable catalogue / web environment for learning resources, keywords are important to the search engine optimization (SEO) strategy of the environment, and are used in conjunction with resource titles, descriptions and other educational information such as target audience to improve the findability of the resource on the web or within the catalogue / registry. Keywords are sometimes called "tags" in non-academic environments.</p> <p>Allowed values: Free text or keywords from a given vocabulary.</p> <p>Example: "Capacity building, Biodiversity data, Data use restrictions"</p> <p>Constraints: Repeatable</p>	
7	License	A license document that applies to this content, typically indicated by URL.	TEXT (100)	<p>Notes: The license is used to represent and classify data access policies related to the LR. It can be a short label indicating the license (e.g., CC BY 4.0) or a full label (e.g., Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International) or the complete definition (e.g., The data are available under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Public License (https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)).</p> <p>Allowed values: Free text or keywords from a given vocabulary, e.g., the NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS), http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L08/current/</p> <p>Example: "Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International"</p> <p>Constraints: Not repeatable</p>	<p>CV recommendations needed. Two elements: URL & Human readable name</p> <p>The NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS), http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L08/current/</p> <p>There is also a more complete CV for license, that is the Licence authority table (AT), a controlled vocabulary listing the European Commission Reuse Notice and the European Union Public Licences. It also provides a list of standard licences available internationally, including the Creative Commons licences. It gives an authority code and labels in most official EU languages. The Licence AT is maintained by the Publications Office of the European Union on the EU Vocabularies website.</p> <p>ID: http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/licence</p>

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8	Version Date	The version date for the most recently published or broadcast resource.	DATE	<p>Notes: This date may relate to either the publication of a new version of a resource or the modification date of an original version. If the original version of a resource is changed significantly, it may be better to create a new description of the newer version rather than change the version date, especially if the older version of the resource will continue to be made available (similar to a new "edition" of a published entity).</p> <p>Allowed values: Date Format: YYYY-MM-DD IETF RFC3339 ISO 8601; To indicate a date range, follow the RKMS-ISO8601 standard for depicting date ranges.</p> <p>Example: "2020-11-12"</p> <p>Constraints: Not repeatable</p>	<p>http://www.lyberty.com/meta/iso_8601.htm; See also http://www.ukoln.ac.uk/metadata/dcmi/collection-RKMS-ISO8601/; check status for latter.</p>
9	URL to Resource	The URL that resolves to the learning resource or to a "landing page" for the resource that contains important contextual information including the direct resolvable link to the resource, if applicable.	TEXT (1000)	<p>Notes: As this value is intended to at least specify where a resource exists and the mechanism for retrieving it at a resolvable location, it should follow the syntax of URL: http://www.domainname.com/folder-name/web-page-file-name.htm. The URL could also point to a "landing page" for the resource that could include other contextual information, especially if the resource is related to others such as a member of a set or collection of resources. Ideally, the URL would also be a persistent identifier (PID) that provides a long-lasting reference to the resource such as those created and supported by PID systems such as Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) or Archival Resource Keys (ARKs).</p> <p>Allowed values: URL syntax</p> <p>Example: "https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mOJRaLwOaCs"</p> <p>Constraints: Not repeatable</p>	
10	Resource URL Type	The designation of identifier scheme used for the resource URL.	TEXT (40)	<p>Notes: It represents the type of the URL of the resource, that is the used scheme (e.g., Web Address URL, DOI, ARK, etc.).</p> <p>Allowed values: Ideally the values used will come from a controlled vocabulary, e.g., the related IdentifierType from DataCite at: https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.2/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.2.pdf</p> <p>Example: DOI</p> <p>Constraints: Not repeatable</p>	<p>See relatedIdentifierType CV from DataCite at: https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.2/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.2.pdf</p>

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11	Target Group (Audience)	The principal users(s) for which the learning resource was designed.	TEXT (40)	<p>Notes: It indicates the target group(s) for which the learning resource has been designed and implemented.</p> <p>Allowed values: free text (or codes from an existing vocabulary).</p> <p>Example: "Data centre staff"</p> <p>Constraints: Repeatable</p>	<p>CV recommendations needed:</p> <p>The Europass Standard List of Target Groups provides a custom vocabulary to describe groups of learners that a learning opportunity, and corresponding credential, is tailored and/or best suited for. http://data.europa.eu/snb/target-group/25831c2</p>
12	Learning Resource Type	The predominant type or kind that characterizes the learning resource.	TEXT (40)	<p>Notes: Different metadata schemes employ this element to indicate other factors regarding the learning resource type. For instance, LOM indicates the potential educational use(s) or type(s) of content associated with the LR, see example below. Other values are indeed relevant only to its format or genre (diagram, figure, graph, index, slide, table, narrative text). The vocabulary terms are defined as in the OED: 1989 and as used by educational communities of practice. LRMI uses a concept scheme for this field which contains broad terms such as Assessment, Unit Plan, Assessment Item, Activity plan, Rubric/Scoring Guide, Educator/Curriculum Guide, Textbook, Lesson Plan, Recorded Lesson. Most of these are based on the common Education Data Standards (CEDS) at https://ceds.ed.gov/element/000928. More specific terms can be expanded using SKOS.</p> <p>Allowed values: Ideally, this list of types should come from a controlled vocabulary that is actively maintained and curated.</p> <p>Example: "Narrative text"</p> <p>Constraints: Not repeatable</p>	<p>CV recommendations needed:</p> <p>See list of CVs at: Here's a link to a couple of controlled vocabularies for a couple of our terms: https://github.com/dcmi/lrmi/blob/master/lrmi_vocab/Vocabulary_inventory/public_vocabularies.md/. This list is associated with the LRMI schema, but could be useful for our purposes. LRMI is also in the process of updating its own "concept scheme" for LR Type. See more about these efforts at: https://github.com/dcmi/lrmi/tree/main/lrmi_vocab/learningResourceType. Issues and feedback on this list can be found at: https://github.com/dcmi/lrmi/issues?q=is%3Aissue+is%3Aopen+label%3ALearningResourceTypes.</p> <p>Another example can be found at: https://wiki.ucar.edu/display/nsd/docs/Type</p>
13	Learning Outcome(s)	The descriptions of what knowledge, skills or abilities students should acquire on completion of the resource.	TEXT (1000)	<p>Notes: It indicates the learning outcomes after the completion of the training resource.</p> <p>Allowed values: free text</p> <p>Example: "At the end of this course the participants will be able to make their research data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR)."</p> <p>Constraints: Repeatable</p>	<p>Possible definition/guidance at: https://www.google.com/url?q=https://www.uclahealth.org/nursing/workfiles/Education%2520Courses/ContinuingEducation/ce-LearningOutcome-v-LearningObjective-052016.pdf&sa=D&source=editors&ust=1621964708148000&usg=AOvVaw1BcOmMDDlhxveT3zqOX0mD</p>

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14	Access Cost	The potential cost associated to the learning resource.	TEXT (8)	<p>Notes: It indicates if the learning resource has an access cost.</p> <p>Allowed values: yes, no, maybe with recommendation that further explanation of “Maybe” goes in the Description field for “It depends” or “It changes” explanations).</p> <p>Example: "no"</p> <p>Constraints: Not repeatable</p>	<p>It can include yes, no, maybe or a more precise indication about cost and access by following the COAR vocabulary (open access; embargoed access; restricted access; metadata only access)</p>
15	Expertise Level	The target skill level in the topic being taught.	TEXT (40)	<p>Notes: It indicates the expertise level required for the specific learning resource.</p> <p>Allowed values: free text (or codes from an existing vocabulary e.g., beginner, intermediate, advanced, etc.)</p> <p>Example: "beginner"</p> <p>Constraints: Not repeatable</p>	CV recommendations needed:
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17					